

Energy / Footprint Efficient Photonic Signal Processing of Raw Photocurrents in Phase-Agnostic Coherent Receiver

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Abstract: Signal recovery is demonstrated for a phase-diversity coherent receiver with free-running LO. After a direct translation of unamplified photocurrents to the optical frequency domain, the signal is processed in a compact silicon micro-ring resonator, at half the energy cost.

1.) Introduction

Coherent detection is moving towards short-reach and cost-sensitive segments, including intra-datacenter and optical access networks [1, 2]. In these realms, simplicity is paramount and demands low-complexity yet highly-efficient receivers and signal processing methods. While the first can be addressed by means of photonic integration [3], processing mostly relies on DSP methods. Self-homodyning can be applied at the expense of additional fiber / cores [4, 5]. Instead, receivers with independent local oscillator (LO) can be optically synchronized [3, 6] or robust RF-based analogue signal processing (ASP) can be adopted to recover real-valued [7] and complex optical modulation [8].

This work extends phase-agnostic coherent signal processing to the photonic domain. The required mathematical functions are applied to a translation of the unamplified photocurrent into the optical frequency space, yielding an efficient processing with low required energy and small footprint with respect to RF-based ASP.

Fig. 1: (a) PSP architecture, (b) photocurrents driving the PSP, (c) response of optical squarer, (d) folded MRR, (e) eye diagrams.

2.) Photonic Signal Processing Architecture

Phase-diversity reception with an optical 90° hybrid and balanced detectors (Fig. 1(a)) results in the photocurrents $i_{phI}(t) \sim s_{OOK}(t) \cdot \cos(\Omega_{IF}t + \varphi(t))$ and $i_{phQ}(t) \sim s_{OOK}(t) \cdot \sin(\Omega_{IF}t + \varphi(t))$ for the I and Q quadratures, with φ and Ω_{IF} denoting the phase noise and intermediate frequency after coherent intradyne detection with a free-running LO. In order to obtain the original on-off keyed (OOK) signal s_{OOK} , envelope detection is performed so that $o(t) = i_{phI}^2(t) + i_{phQ}^2(t)$ yields the OOK data [9]. This involves signal conditioning and 4-quadrant multiplication for RF-based ASP [7, 10]. Instead, the proposed photonic signal processing (PSP) converts the raw I and Q photocurrents (Fig. 1(b)) back to the optical domain. For this an AM-to-FM converter that is fed by the balanced PIN detectors – notably without transimpedance amplifier (TIA). An efficient frequency modulator yields the FM signal $v(t) = v_0 + v_\Delta \cdot i_{ph}(t)$, with v_0 and v_Δ being modulation parameters. The frequency-coded I and Q photocurrents can now be simply squared through a periodic filter function. Figure 1(c) presents the transfer function $\mu(v)$ of a 10-GHz delay interferometer (DI) used as multi- λ squarer. Its periodic transmission is shown over the optical frequency v , relative to a DI notch and together with its theoretical function $\delta(v) = \frac{1}{2} [1 - \cos(2\pi v \cdot \Delta T)]$, with the differential delay ΔT being the inverse of the free spectral range (FSR). There is good overlap with the approximation $\sigma(v) = (\pi v \Delta T)^2$ if we observe $\delta(v)$ at its spectral notch where $|v| < \text{FSR}/4$. Given that (i) the carrier offset v_0 centers the I, Q signals to a DI notch and (ii) the FM deviation v_Δ of these signals is kept small enough to remain in the quadratic region close to the notch, the DI output then becomes $o(t) \sim \sum [\pi v i_{phI,Q}(t) / \text{FSR}]^2$. This yields phase-agnostic coherent detection.

3.) Experimental Setup, PSP Characterisation

An OOK signal is modulated on a wavelength of 1550 nm using a Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM). The data signal is transmitted over 14.3 km before it is detected by a phase-diversity coherent receiver building on a 90° hybrid as optical mixer and a free-running LO (9 dBm) with a detuning smaller than the symbol rate R_{sym} . The input polarization has been manually optimized. However, polarization diversity can be implemented conveniently as shown in [10].

Fig. 2: Experimental setup involving (a) RF-based and (b, c) photonic signal processing for coherent reception. (d) DBR laser tuning through DBR modulation. (e) Electro-optic response of DBR section.

The first implementation for photonic processing, denoted as **PSP-1** in Fig. 2(b), employs independent sideband modulation [11] to simultaneously encode the I, Q photocurrents on the two sidebands of an optical carrier Λ through an optical I/Q modulator (IQM). To do so, the photocurrents at $\Omega_{IF} < R_{sym}$ are frequency modulated on a carrier $f_m = \nu_0 + \nu_{\Delta}/2 = 10$ GHz, with $\nu_{\Delta} = 8$ GHz. These FM representations of the photocurrents are then situated at the lower (I) and upper (Q) sideband. They are processed simultaneously with a 20-GHz DI as an optical squarer since $f_m = FSR/2$. This configuration is shown in Fig. 3(a) for a 5-Gb/s OOK signal, before and after the optical squarer. The bias points of the IQM have been set to suppress the optical carrier Λ , together with a narrowband fiber Bragg grating (FBG) that is centered on Λ to yielding an additional suppression of 6.4 dB.

A simplified PSP implementation is shown in Fig. 2(c) as **PSP-2**. Here, the photocurrents of the balanced PIN photodiodes are directly driving the distributed Bragg reflector (DBR) of a DBR laser used as AM-to-FM converter, without extra RF amplification. The offset frequency ν_0 of the I, Q FM signals is determined by the DBR bias, typically 2-3 mA. The peak-to-peak swing of the photocurrents, which is ~ 100 μ A for a received optical power (ROP) of -25 dBm, is large enough to support a frequency deviation ν_{Δ} matched to the multi- λ squarer (SQU), which is either a 10-GHz DI based on an asymmetric Mach-Zehnder interferometer, or the through-response of the micro-ring resonator (MRR) of Fig. 1(d). The MRR was fabricated on silicon-on-insulator technology. The narrow FSR of 9.3 GHz, with a drop-port FWHM bandwidth of 1.6 GHz, was realized with a folded MRR structure on an area of 220×2050 μ m². An APD+TIA photoreceiver then converts the sum of squared I, Q quadratures to the electrical domain.

The gain section of the DBR laser was biased at 40 mA, yielding an output of 1.4 dBm. Figure 2(d) reports the shift in optical frequency when driving the DBR, after heterodyning the emission with a reference at ~ 1543 nm. The optical frequency ν tunes with 17.9 GHz/mA, enabling a frequency deviation ν_{Δ} wide enough for spectral processing with the DI or MRR (Fig. 1(c)) when driving the DBR section with the unamplified photocurrent of the balanced PIN detector. The response for electro-optic DBR modulation drops sharply after a 3dB-bandwidth of 270 MHz (Fig. 2(e)). This is presently the main limitation of this work and requires optimized DBR lasers for faster e/o modulation, as shown for 10 GHz [12]. The experiment therefore utilizes a low OOK symbol rate of $R_{sym} = 100$ Mb/s to prove the PSP concept. The spectra at the coherent receiver (CRX) input and within the PSP unit are shown in Fig. 3(b) together with the transmission of the DI and prove the spectrally wide I, Q FM signals “oscillating” at the squaring DI notches.

For the **RF-based ASP** (Fig. 2(a)), the signal of the balanced PIN+TIA receivers ($Z_T = 60$ dB Ω) is conditioned by LNAs (10 dB/stage) to address the loss of the 4-quadrant RF multiplier (4QM) required for envelope detection.

Fig. 3: Spectral setup for (a) independent sideband modulated I, Q (PSP-1) and (b) DBR-based FM translation for I, Q (PSP-2).

4.) Reception, Energy & Footprint Performance

Figure 4(a) reports the bit error ratio (BER) performance for photonic (solid lines) and RF-based (dashed lines) processing over ROP.

In case of **PSP-1**, A sensitivity of -34.2 dBm is obtained for 5 Gb/s OOK recovery at a BER of 10^{-3} (\diamond). Recovered 2.5 and 5-Gb/s OOK signals are exemplarily included in Fig. 5. The additional patterning at 5 Gb/s is attributed to the residual optical carrier Λ . This component is suppressed for the 2.5 Gb/s OOK due to use of a 10-GHz DI as squarer, which features a spectral notch at Λ .

For the **PSP-2** based direct-drive scheme, where the balanced photodiodes feed the DBR lasers without extra RF amplification, the PSP method obtains a sensitivity of -30.1 dBm at a BER of 10^{-3} when using the DI as optical squarer (\blacktriangle), as evidenced through a clear eye diagram. When substituting the DI with the more compact MRR, the sensitivity improves by 2.1 dB (\blacklozenge). This is attributed to the smaller bandwidth of the MRR notch, permitting a lower DBR drive and therefore a lower ROP. We did not see a penalty for transmission over 14.3 km of SMF (\blacksquare). The RF-based processing cannot obtain a BER below 5.8×10^{-2} in the direct-drive scenario, even when raising the ROP to 3 dBm.

When using a PIN+TIA instead of the direct PIN drive for the DBR lasers, the performance improves vastly through the transimpedance gain, leading to a sensitivity of -55.7 dBm (\bullet) at the expense of adding an RF circuit to a previously purely opto-electronic receiver layout. Compared to PSP-1 and accounting for the data bandwidth ratio, this means an improvement of 4.5 dB in sensitivity. RF-based ASP achieves a BER of 10^{-3} for a ROP of -39.7 dBm (\times) and cannot compete with the PSP-2 receiver, even after adding one (+) or two (o) more LNAs.

Fig. 4: (a) BER performance and (b) received signal spectra along PSP-2 chain.

Figure 4(b) shows the RF spectra along the **PSP-2** chain for the I photocurrent after coherent detection (α in Fig. 1(a)), after optical squaring (γ) and after summing I and Q (ψ). The corresponding eyes (Fig. 1(e)) include the FM output of the DBR laser (β). The detuning Ω_{IF} in the photocurrent is compensated after PSP (γ), with no further signature of neither Ω_{IF} nor $2\Omega_{IF}$.

Element \ Processing		① Analog RF		② Photonic (PSP-2)		
		mW	mm ²	mW	mm ²	
CRX	LO	1×	84	0.025	84	0.025
	90° hybrid	1×	–	6.10 ⁻⁴	–	6.10 ⁻⁴
	balanced PIN	2×	24	2.10 ⁻³	24	2.10 ⁻³
ASP	TIA	2×	360	1.58	direct drive	
	4Q Multiplier	2×	312	3.75		
PSP	LD gain +	2×			84	0.035
	DBR	2×			6	5.10 ⁻³
	MRR	1×			–	0.451
	APD+TIA	1×			77	0.789
com	micro-TEC	1×	160	shared	160	shared
Total			940	5.36	435	1.31

Table 1: Energy consumption and footprint.

Finally, Table 1 compares the energy and footprint requirements for RF-based ASP with a commercial 4-quadrant multiplier (AD834) and the DBR-based PSP method, assuming a micro-TEC integrated with either receiver assembly. The PSP-2 architecture can capitalize on the efficient AM-to-FM conversion through the DBR lasers, which is compatible with the direct photocurrent drive (down to $\sim 35 \mu A_{pp}$) of the balanced PIN photodiodes, and by the all-

optical squaring function that simultaneously processes multiple input signals. Given the compact space on which the MRR of the multi- λ squarer and an optical 90° hybrid [13] can be realized, it is possible for the PSP-2 to outperform the RF-based method in both, energy consumption (-3.3 dB) and footprint (-6.1 dB).

Fig. 5: OOK signal recovered by the PSP-1 architecture.

5.) Conclusions

An opto-electronic signal recovery circuit involving efficient optical FM, simultaneous squaring and summation of multiple spectral channels has been evaluated for the coherent detection of real-valued signals. The proposed PSP stage does not require RF circuits apart from bias-Ts. Through omission of the TIA, the involved direct-drive for DBR-based AM-to-FM converter greatly simplifies the overall coherent receiver for links with low optical budget, boosting the energy efficiency and compressing the footprint. Scaling up the data rate through high-bandwidth DBRs is left for future work.

6.) Acknowledgements

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7.) References

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